

Assessment of Various Factors Influencing Menstrual Health in Females between Menarche and Menopause

Varshini Erroju^{1*}, Sai Trisha Thatikonda², Jayasri Vodela², Prasanna Uppena², Sai Chaitanya Vangeti², Akansha Puvvula Venkatalaxmi²

1. Assistant professor, Department of Pharmacy, Vaageswari College of Pharmacy, Telangana, India

2. Pharm D, Department of Pharmacy, Vaageswari College of Pharmacy, Telangana, India

*Corresponding author: Varshini Erroju

Received: Aug 18, 2025

Accepted: Sep 10, 2025

Published: Sep 12, 2025

Abstract—

Menstrual health is shaped by physiological, environmental, and lifestyle factors across the female reproductive lifespan. Understanding these influences is vital for identifying patterns and risk factors associated with menstrual irregularities. This study aimed to assess menstrual irregularities and associated symptoms among women from menarche to menopause, and to examine the influence of lifestyle, physiological, and sociodemographic factors, including PCOS and hormonal medication use. A cross-sectional observational study was conducted using an online questionnaire administered via SurveyHeart, with a total of 1,021 participants aged 10–50+ years. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Chi-square tests, Kruskal–Wallis one-way ANOVA, and logistic regression. Significant associations were observed between menstrual irregularities and body mass index (BMI; $p < 0.001$), dietary habits, physical inactivity ($p = 9.78 \times 10^{-18}$), and family history of PCOS ($p < 0.001$). Normal BMI emerged as a protective factor for menstrual regularity (OR = 4.49, 95% CI: 0.56–35.73). These findings highlight the importance of early identification and targeted health education to promote reproductive well-being.

Key words— Menstrual health, menarche, menopause, BMI, lifestyle, PCOS, cross-sectional study.

1. INTRODUCTION

The menstrual cycle is a hallmark of female reproductive health and is often considered a vital sign, reflecting the body's overall physiological and hormonal balance [1], [2]. It represents a complex interplay of neuroendocrine signals originating from the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian (HPO) axis, which regulates the cyclic release of hormones such as follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), luteinizing hormone (LH), estrogen, and progesterone. This finely tuned mechanism not only governs ovulation and fertility but also has significant effects on metabolic, emotional, and cognitive functions throughout a woman's life [1], [3].

The reproductive lifespan of a female typically extends from menarche, the onset of the first menstrual bleeding, to menopause, the cessation of menstrual cycles. These transitional stages are influenced by multiple biological, environmental, nutritional, and socio-cultural factors. The International Federation of Gynecology and

Obstetrics (FIGO) defines a normal menstrual cycle as occurring every 24–38 days, with flow lasting up to 8 days and cycle-to-cycle variation of less than 7–9 days [1], [4]. However, menstrual patterns can vary widely among individuals and across different phases of reproductive life, often reflecting changes in health status, lifestyle, and psychological well-being.

The timing of menarche is considered a key indicator of pubertal development and is influenced by genetic predisposition, nutrition, body weight, physical activity, and exposure to endocrine-disrupting chemicals [5]. In many parts of the world, including India, there is a downward trend in the age of menarche, possibly due to improvements in nutrition and environmental changes [6]. Early menarche is associated with a higher risk of menstrual irregularities, obesity, metabolic syndrome, and reproductive disorders such as polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS), while delayed menarche can signal undernutrition or chronic illness [7].

Menstrual irregularities, such as oligomenorrhea, polymenorrhea, menorrhagia, and amenorrhea, are common throughout adolescence and adulthood. These abnormalities may be physiological, especially during the initial years post-menarche or in perimenopausal women, but can also indicate underlying endocrine or structural pathologies. For instance, PCOS, one of the most common endocrine disorders affecting reproductive-aged women, is characterized by infrequent ovulation, hyperandrogenism, and polycystic ovaries, often presenting as irregular menstrual cycles [8].

Body mass index (BMI) plays a significant role in menstrual health. Both low and high BMI are associated with alterations in the HPO axis, leading to anovulatory cycles, reduced fertility, or excessive menstrual bleeding. Studies have demonstrated that obesity can lead to increased estrogen production from peripheral adipose tissue, which may disrupt the hormonal balance required for normal ovulation and cycle regularity [7], [9]. Conversely, underweight individuals may experience hypothalamic amenorrhea due to energy deficiency.

In addition to physiological factors, psychosocial elements such as stress, emotional well-being, sleep disturbances, and societal stigma significantly impact menstrual health. Chronic stress can suppress hypothalamic GnRH secretion, thereby disrupting the entire hormonal cascade required for ovulation [10]. Moreover, cultural beliefs and myths about menstruation often prevent open discussions, leading to poor menstrual hygiene practices, lack of education, and reluctance to seek medical attention for irregularities [11].

Socioeconomic status, level of education, and access to healthcare further influence menstrual health outcomes. Women from lower socioeconomic backgrounds may experience barriers to menstrual hygiene products, reproductive health services, and awareness regarding normal versus abnormal menstrual patterns. The World Health Organization (WHO) emphasizes the importance of menstrual health education as a key component of reproductive rights and adolescent well-being [12].

Menstrual dysfunction can significantly impact a woman's quality of life, affecting her education, work productivity, self-esteem, and interpersonal relationships. It is not merely a gynecological concern but a broader public health issue, particularly in developing countries where taboos and lack of

resources prevail. Despite its importance, menstrual health remains under-researched and under-reported.

Therefore, a comprehensive understanding of the multifactorial influences on menstrual patterns is essential. This study aims to assess various biological, lifestyle, psychological, and sociodemographic factors that influence menstrual health among females from menarche to menopause. By identifying the patterns and predictors of menstrual irregularities, this research can contribute to better clinical management, health promotion strategies, and policy-making aimed at improving the reproductive health of women.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study Design and Participants

This was a cross-sectional observational survey-based study conducted over a period of four months (March 2025 to June 2025) among females aged 10–55+ years. A structured questionnaire was distributed via the SurveyHeart app. Participants were recruited through online platforms, and informed consent was obtained digitally.

B. Inclusion Criteria

- Females aged between menarche and menopause
- Willing to participate voluntarily
- Provided informed consent

C. Data Collection

The questionnaire captured data on age, weight, height, lifestyle habits (diet, exercise, and sleep), reproductive health conditions, family history of PCOS, and menstrual cycle characteristics.

D. Statistical analysis

Data were analyzed using MS Excel and Jamovi software. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data. Associations between categorical variables were examined using Chi-square tests. The Kruskal–Wallis one-way ANOVA (non-parametric test) was applied to continuous variables across BMI groups with menstrual regularity as the dependent variable. Logistic regression analysis was conducted to identify predictors of menstrual regularity. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

III. RESULTS

A. Age of menarche and duration of menstrual bleeding

A total of 1,021 participants were assessed for the relationship between age at menarche and duration of menstrual bleeding. The majority (n = 476) reported experiencing menarche between 13 and 15 years of age. Across all age groups, the most common bleeding duration was less than 4 days (n = 422). Participants with menarche before the age of 10 years exclusively reported bleeding lasting more than 5 days (n = 81). Those who attained menarche between 10–12 years predominantly reported a bleeding duration of 4–5 days (n = 317), while individuals with late menarche (≥16 years) most commonly reported 4–5 days (n = 66).

TABLE 1: AGE OF MENARCHE AND DURATION OF MENSTRUAL BLEEDING

Menarche Age (years)	<4 Days	4–5 Days	>5 Days	Total
<10			81	81
10–12	81	317		398
13–15	341		135	476
≥16			66	66
Total	422	317	282	1021

Figure 1: Age of Menarche v/s Duration of Menstrual Bleeding

B. Menstrual regularity and reproductive health conditions

Out of the 1,021 participants, 167 (16.4%) reported irregular menstrual cycles, 290 (28.4%) had somewhat regular cycles (30–35 days), and 564 (55.2%) reported very regular cycles (28–30 days). A higher prevalence of irregular cycles was observed

among individuals diagnosed with PCOS (n = 33/88; 37.5%). Participants with thyroid disorders (n = 99) and uterine fibroids (n = 115) mostly reported very regular cycles (n = 61 and n = 68, respectively). Among those with no reported reproductive health conditions (n = 567), a majority (61.2%) also had very regular cycles.

TABLE 2: MENSTRUAL REGULARITY AND REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH CONDITIONS

Condition	Irregular (Varies Each Month)	Somewhat Regular (30–35 Days)	Very Regular (28–30 Days)	Total
CVS	15	16	-	31
DM	9	17	13	39
Endometriosis	17	23	42	82
PCOS	33	22	33	88
Thyroid	15	23	61	99
Uterine Fibrosis	13	34	68	115
None	65	155	347	567
Total	167	290	564	1021

Figure 2: Menstrual Regularity and Reproductive Health Conditions

C. Association between eating habits and menstrual regularity

A Chi-square test revealed a statistically significant association between dietary habits and menstrual cycle regularity ($\chi^2 = 92.36$, $df = 6$, $p < 0.001$). Participants who predominantly consumed homemade or organic food reported a higher prevalence of very regular cycles, whereas those who frequently consumed street food showed a greater tendency toward irregular cycles.

TABLE 3: ASSOCIATION BETWEEN EATING HABITS AND MENSTRUAL REGULARITY

Eating Habits	Irregular menstrual cycle	Somewhat regular (30-35days)	Very regular	Total
As per availability	36	106	170	312
Home made	65	98	280	443
Street food	42	16	45	103
Organic food	09	69	55	163
Total	152	289	580	1021

Figure 3: Association between Eating habits and menstrual regularity

D. BMI categories and menstrual regularity

A Kruskal–Wallis H test was employed to determine differences in menstrual regularity across four BMI categories: underweight, normal weight, overweight, and obese. Results indicated a statistically significant difference ($\chi^2(3) = 605.00, p < 0.001$), with a large effect size ($\epsilon^2 = 0.594$). Post-hoc pairwise comparisons showed significant differences between most BMI group pairs, except between obese and overweight categories, where results were inconclusive.

Participants in the normal BMI category had higher menstrual regularity scores (Mean = 1.97, SD = 0.686) compared to overweight and obese categories (Mean = 3.00). Underweight individuals (n = 17) consistently had the lowest regularity score (Mean = 1.00).

TABLE 4: BMI CATEGORIES AND MENSTRUAL REGULARITY

Variable	χ^2	Df	p-value	Effect Size (ϵ^2)	
Menstrual Regularity	605.00	3	< 0.001	0.594	
Comparison	W		p-value		
Normal vs Obese	9.77		< 0.001		
Normal vs Overweight	33.35		< 0.001		
Normal vs Underweight	0.18		< 0.001		
Obese vs Overweight	NaN		NaN		
Obese vs Underweight	0.83		< 0.001		
Overweight vs Underweight	30.03		< 0.001		
Category	Mean	Median	SD	Min	Max
Underweight	1.00	1	0.00	1	1
Normal	1.97	2	0.686	1	3
Overweight	3.00	3	0.00	3	3
Obese	3.00	3	0.00	3	3
Model	Deviance	AIC	BIC	Nagelkerke	
1	516	530	0.630	0.775	

Figure 4: BMI Categories and Menstrual Regularity

E. Predictors of menstrual regularity

A binomial logistic regression model evaluated the influence of BMI category, physical activity, PCOS history, and healthy eating on menstrual regularity (dichotomized as regular = 1, irregular = 0). The model demonstrated good fit (McFadden’s $R^2 = 0.630$; Nagelkerke $R^2 = 0.775$).

- Physical activity significantly increased the odds of regular menstrual cycles (OR = 4.58, $p < 0.001$).
- A history of PCOS significantly reduced the odds of cycle regularity (OR = 0.20, $p < 0.001$).
- BMI categories showed extremely high odds ratios but were not statistically significant due to sparse data.

- Healthy eating habits were not significantly associated with menstrual regularity ($p = 0.919$).

TABLE 5: PREDICTORS OF MENSTRUAL REGULARITY – LOGISTIC REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Model coefficients							
Predictor	Estimate	SE	Z	P	95% CI for Estimate	Odds Ratio	95% CI for Odds Ratio
Intercept	-3.3191	1.067	-3.112	0.002	[-5.410, 1.229]	0.0362	[0.00447, 0.293]
BMI normal	1.5020	1.058	1.419	0.156	[-0.572, 3.576]	4.4907	[0.56432, 35.736]
BMI overweight	23.7180	795.581	0.030	0.976	[-1435.591, 1533.027]	2.0e+10	[0.00000, ∞]
BMI obese	23.2096	3553.426	0.007	0.995	[-6941.377, 6987.737]	1.2e+10	[0.00000, ∞]
Physical Activity (Yes)	1.5207	0.223	6.808	<0.001	[1.083, 1.959]	4.5756	[2.95336, 7.089]
PCOS History (Yes)	-1.6082	0.419	-3.836	<0.001	[-2.430, 0.786]	0.2002	[0.08804, 0.455]
Healthy Eating (Yes)	0.0230	0.225	0.102	0.919	[-0.419, 0.465]	1.0233	[0.65796, 1.591]

Physical activity significantly increased the odds of having regular menstrual cycles by over 4.5 times (OR = 4.5756, $p < .001$). PCOS history significantly decreased the odds of regularity (OR = 0.2002, $p < .001$). BMI categories showed extremely high and unstable estimates and standard errors, indicating possible data separation or sparse data, and were not statistically significant. Healthy eating habits did not have a significant impact on menstrual regularity ($p = 0.919$).

Assumption checks: Multicollinearity

Predictor	VIF	Tolerance
BMI normal	1.00	1.000
BMI overweight	1.00	1.000
BMI obese	1.00	1.000
Physical Activity	1.02	0.981
PCOS History	1.02	0.984
Healthy Eating	1.02	0.984

IV. DISCUSSION

This study highlights the complex interplay between age at menarche, menstrual regularity, reproductive health conditions, lifestyle factors, and body mass index (BMI), offering critical insights into the determinants of menstrual health in women between menarche and menopause.

A. Age at menarche and duration of bleeding

We observed that early menarche (<10 years) was associated with prolonged menstrual bleeding (>5 days), while those with menarche between 13–15 years reported shorter durations (<4 days). This is consistent with previous findings suggesting that early menarche is linked to prolonged and irregular cycles due to hormonal immaturity [13], [14]. Late menarche (≥ 16 years) was primarily associated with moderate bleeding duration (4–5 days), which may reflect delayed maturation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis [15].

B. Menstrual regularity and reproductive disorders

Our results revealed a strong association between polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) and menstrual irregularity, aligning with existing literature that identifies menstrual disturbances as a primary diagnostic feature of PCOS [16]. Interestingly, participants with thyroid disorders and uterine fibroids mostly reported regular cycles. While hypothyroidism and fibroids are known to influence menstrual flow and pain, regularity may still be preserved, especially in early or subclinical stages [17], [18].

The findings also suggest that individuals without any underlying reproductive condition had a significantly higher prevalence of regular cycles, reinforcing the role of systemic health in maintaining hormonal rhythm and menstrual regularity [19].

C. Impact of eating habits on menstrual cycles

The statistically significant relationship between dietary patterns and menstrual regularity supports previous research linking nutrition and menstrual function. Diets rich in processed or street foods are often low in essential micronutrients (iron, magnesium, B vitamins) and high in trans fats, which may disrupt endocrine function and lead to cycle irregularity [20], [21]. Conversely, balanced diets consisting of homemade or organic foods appear to support hormonal balance and cycle predictability [22].

D. BMI and menstrual regularity

A significant association between BMI categories and menstrual regularity was observed. Underweight and overweight/obese participants showed more irregular cycles compared to those with normal BMI. Obesity is known to affect insulin resistance and estrogen levels, contributing to anovulatory cycles and irregular menstruation [23], [24]. Likewise, low BMI can impair gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) pulsatility, leading to functional hypothalamic amenorrhea [25].

E. Predictors of regularity: regression analysis

Regression findings revealed that physical activity significantly increased the likelihood of regular menstrual cycles, supporting existing evidence that moderate exercise helps regulate the

hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis [26]. A history of PCOS significantly reduced the odds of regular cycles, further reinforcing its adverse impact on menstrual health. Interestingly, healthy eating habits alone did not significantly predict regularity, possibly due to subjective bias in reporting or overlapping influence with other lifestyle factors.

F. Strengths and limitations

This study's strength lies in its large sample size and multifactorial analysis. However, limitations include reliance on self-reported data, potential recall bias, and lack of biochemical validation of conditions such as PCOS or thyroid disorders. Future studies should consider hormonal profiling and longitudinal follow-up to validate and expand upon these findings.

V. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that menstrual health is influenced by a wide range of biological, lifestyle, and reproductive health factors. Early menarche, abnormal BMI, poor dietary habits, and PCOS were strongly associated with menstrual irregularities, whereas physical activity emerged as a protective factor. These findings emphasize the importance of early detection, targeted lifestyle interventions, and comprehensive health education to improve reproductive well-being among women from menarche to menopause.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors sincerely thank all participants for their valuable contributions to this study. We also express gratitude to Vaageswari College of Pharmacy for providing institutional support and resources. The authors acknowledge the use of ChatGPT (OpenAI) for assistance with language editing, formatting guidance, and clarity improvements; the final content was critically reviewed and approved by all authors.

Funding—No external funding was received.

Conflict of Interest—The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethical Approval—The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. As the research involved an anonymous online survey with voluntary participation, and no personally identifiable or clinical data were collected, formal approval from an Institutional Human Ethics

Committee was not required. Informed consent was obtained digitally from all participants before participation.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. S. Fraser, H. O. D. Critchley, M. Broder, and M. G. Munro, "The FIGO recommendations on terminologies and definitions for normal and abnormal uterine bleeding," *Semin. Reprod. Med.*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 383–390, 2011.
- [2] S. D. Harlow, M. Gass, J. E. Hall, et al., "Executive summary of the Stages of Reproductive Aging Workshop +10: addressing the unfinished agenda of staging reproductive aging," *Menopause*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 387–395, 2012.
- [3] M. G. Munro, H. O. D. Critchley, and I. S. Fraser, "The FIGO classification of causes of abnormal uterine bleeding in the reproductive years," *Fertil. Steril.*, vol. 95, no. 7, pp. 2204–2208, 2011.
- [4] M. Mihm, S. Gangooly, and S. Muttukrishna, "The normal menstrual cycle in women," *Anim. Reprod. Sci.*, vol. 124, no. 3–4, pp. 229–236, 2011.
- [5] L. Chiazze Jr., F. T. Brayer, J. J. Macisco Jr., M. P. Parker, and B. J. Duffy, "The length and variability of the human menstrual cycle," *JAMA*, vol. 203, no. 6, pp. 377–380, 1968.
- [6] A. Alvergne and V. Höggqvist Tabor, "Is female health cyclical? Evolutionary perspectives on menstruation," *Trends Ecol. Evol.*, vol. 33, no. 6, pp. 399–414, 2018.
- [7] F. Parazzini, L. Tozzi, and S. Bianchi, "Risk factors for menstrual disorders: the role of body weight," *Gynecol. Endocrinol.*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 355–363, 2000.
- [8] D. Kapoor, R. S. Sandhu, and R. Kaur, "Prevalence of menstrual problems and its effect on quality of life in adolescents," *Int. J. Med. Sci. Public Health*, vol. 5, no. 5, pp. 916–920, 2016.
- [9] J. Bitzer, S. Tschudin, and W. Stadlmayr, "Menstruation and social perception," *Womens Health (Lond.)*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 65–74, 2007.
- [10] S. D. Harlow and O. M. Campbell, "Epidemiology of menstrual disorders in developing countries: a systematic review," *BJOG*, vol. 111, no. 1, pp. 6–16, 2004.
- [11] M. K. C. Nair, D. S. Chacko, M. R. Darwin, K. Padma, and B. George, "Menstrual disorders and menstrual hygiene practices in higher secondary school girls," *Indian J. Pediatr.*, vol. 79, Suppl. 1, pp. S74–S78, 2012.
- [12] World Health Organization, *Adolescent Pregnancy: Issues in Adolescent Health and Development*. Geneva, Switzerland: WHO, 2004.
- [13] A. Golub, "The adolescent transition and the menstrual cycle: A developmental perspective," *Adolesc. Med.*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 229–243, 2002.

[14] D. Apter, "Development of the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis," *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.*, vol. 816, no. 1, pp. 9–21, 1997.

[15] A. E. Treloar, R. E. Boynton, B. G. Behn, and B. W. Brown, "Variation of the human menstrual cycle through reproductive life," *Int. J. Fertil.*, vol. 12, no. 1 Pt. 2, pp. 77–126, 1967.

[16] R. Azziz, K. S. Woods, R. Reyna, T. J. Key, E. S. Knochenhauer, and B. O. Yildiz, "The prevalence and features of the polycystic ovary syndrome in an unselected population," *J. Clin. Endocrinol. Metab.*, vol. 89, no. 6, pp. 2745–2749, 2004.

[17] G. E. Krassas, K. Poppe, and D. Glinde, "Thyroid function and human reproductive health," *Endocr. Rev.*, vol. 31, no. 5, pp. 702–755, 2010.

[18] W. H. Parker, "Uterine fibroids: the controversy surrounding their management," *Obstet. Gynecol. Clin. North Am.*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 629–643, 2000.

[19] S. D. Harlow and O. M. Campbell, "Epidemiology of menstrual disorders in developing countries: a systematic review," *BJOG*, vol. 111, no. 1, pp. 6–16, 2004.

[20] A. J. Gaskins and J. E. Chavarro, "Diet and fertility: a review," *Am. J. Obstet. Gynecol.*, vol. 218, no. 4, pp. 379–389, 2018.

[21] M. Krajewska and M. Chabowski, "Dietary patterns and menstrual health in young women: a review," *Nutrients*, vol. 12, no. 6, p. 1658, 2020.

[22] N. Rafique and M. H. Al-Sheikh, "Prevalence of menstrual problems and their association with psychological stress in young female students studying health sciences," *Saudi Med. J.*, vol. 39, no. 1, pp. 67–73, 2018.

[23] T. M. Barber, P. Hanson, M. O. Weickert, and S. Franks, "Obesity and polycystic ovary syndrome: implications for pathogenesis and novel management strategies," *Clin. Med. Insights Reprod. Health*, vol. 13, pp. 1–8, 2019.

[24] S. Wei, M. D. Schmidt, T. Dwyer, R. J. Norman, and A. J. Venn, "Obesity and menstrual irregularity: associations with SHBG, testosterone, and insulin," *Obesity (Silver Spring)*, vol. 17, no. 5, pp. 1070–1076, 2009.

[25] M. P. Warren and N. E. Perloth, "The effects of intense exercise on the female reproductive system," *J. Endocrinol.*, vol. 170, no. 1, pp. 3–11, 2001.

[26] M. J. De Souza, B. E. Miller, A. B. Loucks, A. A. Luciano, L. S. Pescatello, C. G. Campbell, et al., "High frequency of luteal phase deficiency and anovulation in recreational women runners: blunted elevation in follicle-stimulating hormone observed during luteal-follicular transition," *J. Clin. Endocrinol. Metab.*, vol. 83, no. 12, pp. 4220–4232, 1998.